

ПОКАЗНИКИ СИСТЕМНОГО ЗАПАЛЕННЯ, РІВНІ IGG/IGM ТА D-ДИМЕРУ У ПАЦІЄНТІВ З ФІБРИЛЯЦІЄЮ ПЕРЕДСЕРДЬ ЗАЛЕЖНО ВІД ПЕРЕНЕСЕНОЇ ІНФЕКЦІЇ COVID-19

INDICATORS OF SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION, IGG / IGM AND D-DIMER LEVELS IN PATIENTS WITH ATRIAL FIBRILLATION DEPENDING ON PREVIOUS COVID-19 INFECTION

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Introduction: It is known that atrial fibrillation (AF) is not only one of the most common arrhythmias, and the most frequent rhythm disturbance in patients who have had a SARS-CoV-2 infection.

The aim of our study was to evaluate the indicators of systemic inflammation and to analyze the IgG and IgM levels in patients with atrial fibrillation (AF) depending on the past coronavirus infection (CI).

Material and methods of research: We examined 167 patients aged 62.5 + 0.09 years with paroxysmal or persistent forms of AF in sinus rhythm. 118 people had a history of an average of 6.2 + 0.5 months ago of COVID-19 infection. They made up the 1st group of examined patients. The remaining 49 patients did not have a history of this infection. They constituted the 2nd group of the study, which was the control group. The level of IgG and IgM and D-dimer was determined only in patients of the 1st group on the apparatus "Beckman Coulter Inc."

Results of the study: After a more detailed analysis, we found that in the group of patients with a history of CI had higher markers of systemic inflammation, such as rheumatoid factor (respectively 10.51 + 1.45 U / ml and 4.64 + 0.26, p<0.001) and "C" reactive protein (in groups 5.29 + 0.025 mg/l and 3.54 + 0.10 mg/l, p<0.001). Assessment of the level of IgG and IgM and D-dimer, as the most important predictor of thromboembolism, depending on the increase in the frequency of paroxysms of AF, are given in Table 1:

Indicator	Increase in the frequency of paroxysms	The frequency of paroxysms did not change	p
IgG	7,84±0,41	9,11±0,33	<0,05
IgM	0,97±0,26	0,46±0,40	n.s.
D-dimer	0,29±0,19	0,27±0,20	n.s.

Table 2 shows the same indicators, depending on the increase in the duration of paroxysms:

Indicator	Increased duration of paroxysms	Duration of paroxysms did not change	p
IgG	8,00±0,52	8,11±0,68	n.s.
IgM	1,07±0,2	0,20±0,11	<0,05
D-dimer	0,29±0,19	0,27±0,20	n.s.

Conclusion: In patients with AF, after undergoing CI, activation of systemic inflammation is observed, and as a result, an increase in the electrical instability of the atria. Besides that, we can state that a sufficient acquired immunity, as evidenced by a sufficiently significant increase in IgG, contributes to a more stable course of AF. And this is confirmed by the fact that even a slight (within the norm) increase in IgM can be a marker of an increase in the duration of arrhythmia paroxysms. It is important to note that the level of D-dimer was not associated with the course of AF, which, however, does not reduce the risk of thromboembolism in patients with this rhythm disturbance.